

Catastrophic forgetting and replaying experience: A proposal for augmenting the current replay buffer strategies

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1 Introduction: Sequential Learning

The classic machine learning setting involves learning the distribution of data which is assumed to be i.i.d. In recent years ML has evolved to encompass applications that falls outside the i.i.d regime. When the data is *sequential* one encounters situations where the distribution is changing continually or that there is temporal correlation violating the i.i.d assumption. Examples include, incremental learning, time series and reinforcement learning. This note explores the challenges faced when dealing with changing data distribution, \mathcal{D}_t , where the subscript t represents an ordered sequence such as time or training iterations. In the context of reinforcement learning \mathcal{D}_t will correspond to the experiences collected by the policy after being trained for t iterations/epochs. Since the weights of the policy network are continually changed the distribution of the experiences collected by the policy will also change throughout the training. It is instructive to think of training a neural net under changing data distribution \mathcal{D}_t as learning a new *task* corresponding to the information contained in \mathcal{D}_t .

The challenge in the sequential learning setting such as RL is twofold. First, learning from later tasks might interfere with previously learned tasks: the weights of the neural network associated with a given task might be altered by learning a new task resulting in a performance degradation on previously learned task known as *catastrophic forgetting*. While one needs to stabilise the performance on old tasks, it is imperative to continue learning from recent experiences as well. This is known as the *stability-plasticity* dilemma and has parallels in learning in human brain [8].

2 Strategies to deal with forgetting

2.1 Catastrophic forgetting

Forgetting in neural networks when learning multiple *tasks* has been recognised very early in the development of ML [1][2][3]. A useful way of characterising a *task* in ML is as a collection of input-output mappings that need to be learned by the network. In RL a *task* in this perspective would be learning to take particular set of actions for a certain configurations of environments states (ex. picking up an object when within the reach). Given task-A and task-B with input-output pairings $\{X_i^A, y_i^A\}$, $\{X_i^B, y_i^B\}$ resp, a neural network, $f(\cdot|\theta)$ with the capacity to learn task-A will have a non-empty solution space A_S for its weights corresponding to task-A, i.e

$$A_S = \{\theta | f(X_i^A | \theta) = y_i^A, \forall i\} \tag{1}$$

Having the ability to learn both task-A and task-B will then mean that there is a non-empty overlapping region $A_S \cap B_S$ (when these regions are disjoint the architecture of the network must be expanded/changed to be able to learn both tasks). The over-parameterisation in deep learning ensures the existence of this non-empty overlapping region. In sequential learning, learning task-A first would

(a) Sequential learning: task-1 is learned before task-2

(b) Concurrent learning: task-1 and task-2 are learned together

Figure 1: Sequential Vs Concurrent training: Shaded regions depict solution regions for the respective tasks and solid region is the overlapping solution region

mean finding a learning trajectory for the weights that ends in the space $\theta \in A_S$, however, subsequent training on task-B may result in pulling the weights into the region $B_S \setminus A_S$ thus losing all knowledge about task-A. It is reasonable to expect that concurrent training on both task-A and task-B will result in a learning trajectory towards the overlapping region $A_S \cap B_S$, as one would intuitively expect the gradient of the loss function evaluated on task-A data, $\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(X^A, y^A)$, would roughly point towards the region A_S as we expect at least a local minima with respect to task-A to lie in this region. The heuristic argument then is that combining both task-A and task-B data would result in a gradient direction towards $A_S \cap B_S$ (see Fig: 1)

A proxy for measuring the performance on task-A is the expectation of the loss-function used in the algorithm with respect to the data distribution of the task, \mathcal{D}_A

$$\mathbb{E}_{Z \sim \mathcal{D}_A} [\mathcal{L}(Z; \theta)] \tag{2}$$

If the weights after learning task A is θ_A and the weights after learning task-B is θ_B , forgetting of task-A happens when,

$$\mathbb{E}_{Z \sim \mathcal{D}_A} [\mathcal{L}(Z; \theta_B)] > \mathbb{E}_{Z \sim \mathcal{D}_A} [\mathcal{L}(Z; \theta_A)] \tag{3}$$

There is a possibility that the interference due to learning a later task is beneficial to the learning. This is known as *backward transfer* and characterised by,

$$\mathbb{E}_{Z \sim \mathcal{D}_A} [\mathcal{L}(Z; \theta_B)] < \mathbb{E}_{Z \sim \mathcal{D}_A} [\mathcal{L}(Z; \theta_A)] \tag{4}$$

The above characterisation of *catastrophic forgetting* points to strategies to overcome this phenomenon which we broadly classify as,

1. Replay based
2. Regularisation based
3. Network expansion (dynamic architectures) / parameter isolation

Replay Based Replay based methods store data / representation of previous tasks and use it to either mix with current training data or to constrain the current learning to not affect previously learned *tasks* (ex, constraining gradient updates to a feasible region). **Replay methods will be the main focus of this note especially in relation to reinforcement learning and will be explored in greater detail in the coming sections.**

Regularisation Based Regularisation based methods augment the loss function with a penalty that protects the previously learned information [4] [5][6][7]. These algorithms measure the importance of a parameter θ_i for task-A, w_i , using some proxy and give higher penalty for any change due to learning task-B. Given the learned optimal parameters for the task-A, $\{\theta_i^A\}$, the loss function is in general augmented as

$$\mathcal{L}(Z; \theta) \rightarrow \mathcal{L}(Z; \theta) + \lambda \sum_i w_i (\theta_i - \theta_i^A)^2 \quad (5)$$

Two of the important and successful algorithms in this class are Elastic Weight Consolidation (EWC) [4] and Memory Aware Synaptic Consolidation (MAS) [5]. The penalty for EWC is given by estimating the posterior probability of the parameters given the dataset for task-A, $p(\theta|\mathcal{D}_A)$, as a Gaussian distribution with mean θ^A and precision (inverse covariance) given by Fisher Information matrix. Considering only diagonal elements, this gives the weight of this regularisation scheme as

$$w_i = \mathbb{E}_{Z \sim \mathcal{D}_A} [(\partial_{\theta_i} \mathcal{L}(Z; \theta)|_{\theta^A})^2] \quad (6)$$

The importance weight for MAS is calculated using the sensitivity of the output of the network, $F(Z; \theta)$ to a change in the parameter around the optimal parameters for task-A, θ^A ,

$$w_i = \mathbb{E}_{Z \sim \mathcal{D}_A} \left\| \partial_{\theta_i} F(Z; \theta) \Big|_{\theta^A} \right\| \quad (7)$$

Parameter Isolation Network expansion / parameter isolation can be used in the presence of explicitly defined tasks. Here either each task is allocated a certain set of parameters and learning happens while freezing the weights of related to other tasks.

2.2 Gradient based characterisation of continual/multi-task learning

2.3 Reinforcement learning as a sequential learning problem

In Reinforcement learning the data that is used for training is collected via the interaction with the environment. When the data collection is made using a network while it is being trained the distribution of the data changes as the training proceeds. This is especially significant in actor-critic methods that uses the policy being trained as the collection policy. Here the distribution of the transitions depend on the policy weights at at iteration t , θ_t ,

$$(s_i, a_i, s_{i+1}) \sim \mu(s_i) \pi(a_i | s_i; \theta_t) p(s_{i+1} | s_i, a_i) \quad (8)$$

Here μ, π, p are stationary distribution of the policy, policy distribution and transition kernel resp. Here the transitions are from a distribution that changes with the ordered sequence of training iterations hence exhibiting the characteristics of the sequential learning problem.

2.3.1 Task in reinforcement learning

A task in reinforcement learning can be interpreted as a given behaviour of the policy in response to a subset of states, ie a collection $\{s_i, a_i\}$. This abstract notion of *task* will be directly related to the policy being learned as it constitutes the state action mapping or distribution learned by the policy. The challenge in the sequential learning setting is to protect any learned beneficial behaviour of the policy at training iteration t while continuing to train further on iterations $t' > t$. Storing a copy of the policy at different training iterations in order to remember past behaviours will generally be infeasible and inefficient. The replay methods for dealing with this problem rely on the assumption that the behaviour of the policy at t can be captured by the data/ transition distributions it generates,

$$s_i^t, a_i^t, s_{i+1}^t, r_{i+1}^t \sim \mathcal{D}_{\pi_t} \tag{9}$$

2.3.2 On applying techniques for catastrophic forgetting for reinforcement learning

The strategies described above are in general applicable for any sequential learning problem. The solution depends on identifying the sequential nature of learning and the abstraction notion of *task* in any particular setting. Some methods are more suitable than others depending on the problem. For example *parameter isolation* is more suited when there are clearly distinguishable task boundaries. For reinforcement learning the sequence as explained above can be identified as the training iteration which entails that the data collected by the policy after the t 'th update will $\pi(\cdot|s; \theta_t)$ will correspond to task- t . In practice though the change in policy after one gradient update will be too slight to constitute a different task and it may be useful to consider an epoch of training iterations and the data (transitions) collected during this period as constituting a behaviour A, ex, $\mathcal{D}_A = \{\text{transitions collected by the policy during the first 1000 iterations}\}$. Once this identification is made it is plausible to modify the above strategies for reinforcement learning.

2.4 Experience replay in Reinforcement Learning

A useful categorization of experience replay methods is on account of *what is replayed?* and *how it is replayed?*.

2.4.1 Replay of past input

In order to remember behaviours one can reuse the *raw data* that was used to train the network, known as veridical inputs this is generally know as *experience rehearsal* and usually facilitated by storing experiences in a buffer (replay buffer). We will primarily be focused on strategies associated with replay buffer in this note.

2.4.2 Replay of representations of input

In analogy with biological systems what is replayed can be a representation of the past data rather than the data itself. The hippocampus has been observed to replay recent experiences/ memory during sleep which is transferred to the cortex for long-term memory [8]. In deep learning the representations will in general be the outputs of intermediate layers of the neural network which can be stored and reused for training. Given a neural net $F(G(Z; \theta_G); \theta_F)$ and a loss function $\mathcal{L}(F(G(Z), Z)$, it is possible to store representation of the input Z as $G(Z)$. The optimization objective will then be

$$\min_{\theta_F} \mathbb{E}_{G \sim \mathcal{D}_{\text{replay}}} [\mathcal{L}(F(G; \theta_F))] \tag{10}$$

2.4.3 Generative replay of data

Rehearsal of past experiences or representations can also be generated by a network such as GAN as opposed to replaying from memory [10][11][12][13]. This is also inspired by human brain where there are regions specialised for long-term consolidation of memories by generating dreams [8].

3 Replay buffer in reinforcement learning

Replay buffer is a data structure for storing past data used for training. In RL the data is usually the sequence of state, action, reward tuples, (s_t, a_t, r_t) , generated when the agent interacts with the environment. The transitions are stored contiguously in the order of time-steps. Particularly, in actor-critic methods when the training policy is used to collect the transitions collection is made for a fixed number of environment steps before each training update (gradient update of actor and critic) and stored in the replay buffer. The replay buffer is commonly modelled as a FIFO data structure in terms of additions and removals. If one measures the *age* of a policy in terms of the training updates it has gone through, then the data in earlier locations of the replay buffer will reflect older transitions thus capturing previously learned tasks as explained above. A useful way to characterise the RL hyper-parameters in the context of replay buffer is elucidated in [9]. The *capacity*, N , of the replay buffer is the total number of transitions that can be stored in the buffer. The *replay ratio*, C , is the number of environment steps collected per training iteration. Hence the *age of the oldest policy*, will be given by,

$$\text{Age} = \frac{N}{C} \tag{11}$$

3.1 Replay buffer: stability and performance degradation in RL training

Here we give a brief outline on how replay buffer strategies affect the *stability* and *forgetting/ performance degradation with time* of RL training. It is easier to consider the simplest replay buffer strategy, namely a uniform replay buffer where each training update is made with a mini-batch uniformly sampled with replacement.

stability In online RL algorithms the data used for training is a contiguous batch of transitions collected by the training policy just before the update. Thus there will be a strong temporal correlation between the transitions breaking the i.i.d paradigm of learning. Uniform replay buffer provides a uniform shuffling of the transitions when sampled as mini-batch. If the time-horizon (episode length) of an environment is T and the size of the replay buffer is N , then the probability that there are *no transitions from the same episode* in a mini-batch of size M is,

$$\left(1 - \frac{T}{N}\right) \left(1 - \frac{2T}{N}\right) \dots \left(1 - \frac{(M-1)T}{N}\right) \tag{12}$$

This probability clearly increases with N and shows how temporal correlations are reduced when using a replay buffer based training.

performance degradation / forgetting In online learning the training is done using the most recent policy and the behaviour learned in older policies can be forgotten due to the interference from the most recent data distribution. This phenomenon known as *catastrophic forgetting* was discussed in preceding sections. If we denote the policy at training iteration t as $\pi^t(a|s)$ then sampling from the uniform replay buffer of capacity N with replay ratio of 1 will give rise to the following *effective*, (see proof (??)) policy distribution if the current training iteration is t

$$\pi_{\text{replay-buffer}}(a|s) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=t-N+1}^t \pi^i(a|s) \tag{13}$$

Here we can see that the replay buffer induces a policy distribution that is an average of the past N policies thus retaining a some of the past behaviour throughout training.

4 The proposed design of the replay buffer

The simplest design of the replay buffer is a FIFO queue of a sequence transitions, $\tau_t = (s_t, a_t, s_{t+1}, r_t)$ generated when the policy interacts with the environment. A replay buffer of size N will contain the most recent N transitions collected by the policy, $\{\tau_{t-N+1} \dots \tau_t\}$. At each training update a predefined size of mini-batch of transitions are selected with uniform probability with replacement. Any improvement over this basic scheme raises two important questions. (*sampling*) *How are the transitions sampled from the buffer?* and (*retention*) *What experiences are removed when the buffer is full?* The answer to these questions depend on the utility of a given transition for RL learning. In this section we propose some *proxies* that can be used as scores to prioritize transitions to be sampled and retained in the replay buffer.

4.1 Scores to measure utility of the transitions

4.1.1 Surprise (temporal difference)

The temporal difference error (td-Error) on a transition τ is given by,

$$\delta(\tau) = R_t + \gamma \hat{Q}(s_{t+1}, a_{t+1}) - Q(s_t, a_t) \tag{14}$$

This is a proxy for the deviation of current Q-network from the true value and thus presents a higher learning potential for Q networks. The absolute value $|\delta(\tau)|$ proposed as priority score in [18] has been quite successful in DQN type agents. However for actor-critic methods transitions with high td-error will hinder the training of actor-networks as discussed in, here we propose to prioritize the transitions with smaller td-error for actor training as espoused in [19]

4.1.2 Future directed scores

A transitions utility can also be measured by the trajectory that it triggers give the current policy. The following scores based on this observation. *Here we note a potential down side to computing these scores, that it necessitates keeping a cache of transitions until an episode finishes to compute the score and hence computationally expensive*

Future episodic reward The observation that rewarding events leading to higher future reward leads to the following proxy for a given transition $\tau_t = (s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1})$,

$$s(\tau_t) = \sum_{s=t}^T r_s \tag{15}$$

Policy entropy over the trajectory

$$s(\tau_t) = \sum_{s=t}^T \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi} [\log \pi(a|s_t)] \tag{16}$$

Note that this can be quite expensive to compute for continuous action spaces as we need to compute sample average at every step

Future 1-step td-error

$$s(\tau_t) = \frac{1}{T-t+1} \sum_{s=t}^T |\delta(\tau_t)| \tag{17}$$

Most of the methods using a replay buffer use FIFO data structure as described above. However the differences come from *sample selection* and *sample weighting* during gradient update. The following sections will comprise a detailed look at some salient strategies involving replay buffers.

4.1.3 Coverage maximisation

In order to maximise the coverage of the entire state-space *rarer* transitions can be up-sampled and vice versa for *frequent* transitions. The following proxy described in (5.1.2) achieves this

$$s(\tau_i) = -|\{\tau_j \in \text{k-nearest-neighbours} \mid \text{dist}(\tau_i, \tau_j) \leq d\}| \quad (18)$$

4.1.4 Exploration potential

A proxy for encouraging exploration that deviates from the current policy is to compute the deviation distance of the actions. Given a transition $\tau = (s, a, s', r)$ and action $\bar{a} \sim \pi(a|s)$ from the current policy,

$$s(\tau) = \alpha \|a - \bar{a}\| \quad (19)$$

4.1.5 Reservoir sampling for retention

Keeping all the transitions seen so far is the simplest strategy to remember past behaviour, however this is frequently not feasible given the memory constraints and the large amount environment steps needed for convergence in RL. An alternative strategy is to treat each transition generated during the interaction with the environment fairly. Reservoir sampling is a well known retention scheme where given a stream of data and a fixed memory size N , the probability that any data point seen so far is in the memory is guaranteed to be,

$$p(\tau \in \mathcal{B}) = \min\left(\frac{N}{t}, 1\right) \quad (20)$$

Where the t is the number of data-points or transitions seen so far. An optimal algorithm to achieve this is to assign a random score to each arriving transition and keep the smallest N of them in the buffer [16]

4.1.6 Cosine similarity for retention

If a task associated with a sample can be characterised by the direction of the gradient of the loss function on that sample, then this points to a way of storing samples that are diverse (angles between them are bigger). [25] poses this as an optimisation problem on sample selection for the replay buffer. Given a set of samples of size N , the goal is to select $M < N$ samples such that the solid of angle of the feasible region defined in is minimized. They also provide a greedy alternative where the samples are scored with the following proxy that measures the *likeness* of the sample with the samples in the buffer, namely,

$$s(\tau) = \frac{\langle \nabla L(\tau), g_k \rangle}{\|\nabla L(\tau)\| \|g_k\|} \quad (21)$$

Here g_k are the gradients of the loss function with respect to uniformly randomly selected set of samples from the replay buffer (computational restriction that avoids computing the gradient of all the samples in the buffer) and $L(\tau)$ is the loss-function evaluated on the transition τ . We propose the following replay buffer retention strategy for RL using this scheme. At a predefined training interval K , sample a batch of N transitions uniformly storing their gradients in a cache. Now, each transition collected by the driver is assigned the score (21). When the buffer is full a random sample is selected for replacement by the probability based on the score as computed in (4.1.7).

4.1.7 Converting scores to probabilities

Here we discuss how a generic score of a transition as described above can be used for the prioritized sampling of the replay buffer. The score of a transition can be used for both *sampling* and *retention* with the way the score is used to assign priorities will be reversed, i.e $s(\tau_1) > s(\tau_2)$ will mean the

priority of τ_1 is greater than the priority of τ_2 while *sampling* and the reverse when *retaining*, and *vice versa*. A widely used method to convert scores in to probabilities is to use a smoothing parameter α and normalizing by the sum. Given the score $s(\tau)$, the probability associated with this transition will be given by,

$$p(\tau) = \frac{s(\tau)^\alpha + \epsilon}{\sum_{\tau' \in \mathcal{B}} (s(\tau')^\alpha + \epsilon)} \quad (22)$$

Where \mathcal{B} is the replay buffer. ϵ provides a lower-bound for the scores to avoid the situation where some transitions are never sampled. The role of the score in determining the prioritization will be reversed when the sign of α changes. When $\alpha > 0$, $s(\tau_1) > s(\tau_2) \implies p(\tau_1) > p(\tau_2)$ and *vice versa*. This points to a way to use the same score for both *retention* and *sampling* by using smoothing parameter of opposite signs. This is usually a hyper-parameter of the algorithm to be tuned. Another widely used strategy to protect against outliers is to use the rank (ascending) of the scores. Suppose one wants to prioritize higher scores, then a rank based prioritization will be,

$$p(\tau) = \frac{w(\tau)^\alpha + \epsilon}{\sum_{\tau' \in \mathcal{B}} (w(\tau')^\alpha + \epsilon)} \quad w(\tau) = \text{rank}(s(\tau)) \quad \alpha > 0 \quad (23)$$

Ranking also provides a way to deal with negative scores. If the most-negative score is known before hand one can also shift the scores by a constant to make them positive.

4.2 Learning mechanisms to reduce interference and improve transfer

Here we propose some techniques from continual learning literature that can be used to augment RL learning in a way that future learning does not interfere with the past learning while not prohibiting any beneficial transfer.

4.2.1 Gradient projection

We propose an experimental method that is inspired by [17] for RL training. Having a small replay buffer improves the plasticity for learning new tasks faster however it can quickly lead to catastrophic forgetting as discussed above. We propose to employ two buffers a large buffer and a small buffer both FIFO. The RL agent uses the smaller buffer for training actor and critic. The large buffer is used to retain the samples generated by the policy, this buffer is split into M consecutive regions each of which storing m transitions. We use these M regions containing m samples as representing the behaviour of the past policies. At predefined intervals of training iterations, the gradients on these M batches are computed and stored, $g_i, i \in [1, \dots, M]$. At each training update the gradients computed for actor and critic, say g is projected as proposed in [17]. Namely,

$$\begin{aligned} & \operatorname{argmin}_{\tilde{g}} \|\tilde{g} - g\| \\ \text{s.t. } & \langle \tilde{g}, g_i \rangle \geq 0 \quad \forall_i \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

This projection (optimisation) can be performed by the quadratic programming methodology suggested in [17]. The constraint here prevents the current gradient update to the networks from increasing the loss on evaluated on past transitions that are characteristic of past policy behaviour.

4.2.2 Meta learning

Given two batches of data X_1, X_2 representing different tasks and the current weights of the network θ_1 , the following sequence of gradient updates can be made $\theta_{i+1} \leftarrow \theta_i - \alpha \nabla_{\theta_i} L(X_i; \theta_i)$ for $i = 1$ followed by $i = 2$. Now update the new weights θ_4 as follows,

$$\theta_4 \leftarrow \theta_1 + \beta(\theta_3 - \theta_1) \quad (25)$$

Remarkably it was shown in [20] that, if we consider β as a step size and $\tilde{g} = (\theta_3 - \theta_1)$ as an *effective gradient*, then the *effective loss function* associated with \tilde{g} will be,

$$L_{eff} = L(X_1, \theta_1) + L(X_2, \theta_1) - \alpha \langle \nabla_{\theta_1} L(X_1; \theta_1), \nabla_{\theta_1} L(X_2; \theta_1) \rangle \quad (26)$$

Here we have the effect of concurrent learning on task-1 and task-2 augmented by term that maximizes the inner-product of the gradients on each task thus minimizing interference. This can be generalized to multiple iterations representing concurrent training on multiple tasks effectively doing 2nd order gradient update. In [21] uses this gradient update for RL training where multiple batches are sampled from a replay buffer (employing reservoir sampling) and the above gradient update is made iteratively, first with the batch and then across the batch. This is shown to improve the transfer learning and reduce forgetting during the training.

4.2.3 Regularized learning to protect past behaviour

As discussed in (2.3) RL can be interpreted as a sequential learning problem. The learned policy snapshots after different training epochs, e.g policy weights after training iterations 1000, 2000, \dots , can be characterised as different learnt behaviours or tasks. In this interpretation protecting the past learnt behaviour becomes tantamount for successful training. We propose an adaptation of the regularisation methods discussed in (2.1) for RL training. At predefined intervals of length, N training iterations, defining different *epochs* of learning, one takes a copy of the current RL policy and/or critic network. The current learnt weights, θ^k , will then abstractly correspond to the presently learned behaviour after epoch k . These weights, θ^k can then be used to augment the loss function, $\mathcal{L}(\theta)$ with a regularisation penalty discussed in (2.1), namely,

$$\hat{\mathcal{L}}(\theta^k) = \mathcal{L}(\theta^k) + \alpha \sum_i w_i \left(\theta_i^k - \theta_i^{(k-1)} \right)^2 \quad (27)$$

Here θ^k are the current training parameters for the epoch k . When a new training *epoch*, k starts an important question that needs to be answered is how the current training weights θ^k are initialized. The choices here can be broadly classed as,

1. Copy previous epoch weights $\theta^k \leftarrow \theta^{k-1}$
2. Initialize a new set of weights
3. Inject noise or reset the weights of previous epoch $\theta^k \leftarrow \theta^{k-1} + \text{noise}$. Here one can employ a resetting mechanism as proposed in [33][34]

This loss function can be further generalised by having a predefined number, L , of past snapshots of the weights used for regularisation, namely

$$\hat{\mathcal{L}}(\theta) = \mathcal{L}(\theta) + \sum_{j=1}^L \alpha_j \left(\sum_i w_i^{(k-j)} \left(\theta_i - \theta_i^{(k-j)} \right)^2 \right) \quad (28)$$

Here θ^j, w^j are the training weights of the networks and regularisation weights at the end of j^{th} epoch resp. denotes the snap-shot of weights after k^{th} epoch of training.

Remark: It is important to note that we can use a much smaller replay buffer for RL training in order to increase the plasticity. This is expected not to cause a lot of interference since the past behaviour is protected by regularisation.

5 Literature Survey

5.1 Sample selection strategies using priority score

Here we list some of the *proxies* that have been used in the literature for prioritizing the samples stored in the replay buffer.

5.1.1 Actor-prioritized sampling

In [19] the authors investigate the negative effects of using the prioritized sampling based on temporal-difference error in actor-critic algorithms. The transitions with very high TD error correspond to the state-action regions where the critic network diverges from the true value. Even though these samples present a higher learning potential for the critic-network by correcting itself using the gradients computed on these transitions, they give a highly inaccurate gradients for the policy networks as most actor-losses incorporate the value of the critic-network in their functional form ex policy-gradient of DDPG or GAC [22][23]. This work proposes the use of three sampling strategies for combined training. At each training iteration a batch of samples are drawn according to the following sampling probabilities. Given a sample of transition τ and the TD-error $\delta(\tau_i)$

1. **PER sampling:** Draw samples according to the probability, $P(\tau_i) = \frac{\delta(\tau_i)^\alpha}{\sum_{\tau_j} \delta(\tau_j)^\alpha}$ where $\alpha > 0$

2. **Inverse PER sampling:** $P(\tau_i) = \frac{\delta(\tau_i)^\alpha}{\sum_{\tau_j} \delta(\tau_j)^\alpha}$ where $\alpha < 0$

3. **Uniform sampling**

[19] proposes using a mini-batch based on PER sampling for updating the critic network while using the inverse PER sampling to update the actor-network. Further both actor-critic networks are trained together on uniformly sampled mini-batch. Approach makes sense as a heuristic since a low TD-error may suggest a better prediction of the Q network, thus the actor-gradients can be expected to be closer to the *true-values*. We remark that the paper uses $\alpha = -1$ for inverse PER sampling. This however is not necessary as any $\alpha < 0$ will give a higher probability to low TD-error samples and is a hyper-parameter to be tuned.

5.1.2 Coverage maximisation

[24] presents a principled way to investigate sample selection and retention strategies inspired by neuroscientific literature. They reinterpret TD-error based prioritized sampling as *surprise* in biological context where surprising events have been known to be replayed in memory [14] [15]. Moreover they suggest future episodic reward of a transition as a proxy for prioritizing transitions in replay buffer. Notice however that assigning the reward as a score for prioritisation will tend to have an asymmetrical impact in finite horizon environments where the states occurring in the beginning of episode are distinct from the ones occurring towards the end (ex. when time index is included in the state). The sampling strategy that is reported to be the most performant is the one that tries to achieve a **uniform distribution over all visited states** named coverage maximisation. Here transitions are weighted according to the number of neighbouring transitions within a certain predefined distance d and a metric dist . Namely, the score assigned to a transition τ_i ,

$$s(\tau_i) = -|\{\tau_j \in \mathcal{B} : \text{dist}(\tau_i, \tau_j) \leq d\}| \quad (29)$$

5.1.3 Gradient based prioritization

[25] gives a principled investigation into the continual learning problem in general as described in . They characterise different tasks or stages of the continual learning problem as direction of the

gradients generated at different stages of the training. Even though this work focuses on continual learning problems general, it gives a prioritization scheme for scoring transitions in RL given a replay buffer. The score of a transition τ is given by

$$\text{score}(\tau) = \max_{\tau' \in \mathcal{B}_s} \frac{\langle \nabla L(\tau), \nabla L(\tau') \rangle}{\|\nabla L(\tau)\| \|\nabla L(\tau')\|} \quad (30)$$

Here the heuristic behind adopting the above scoring scheme is that, given a randomly selected batch of transitions from the buffer \mathcal{B}_s , the transition that gives higher cosine similarity for the gradient direction with the transitions in the batch has greater generalization and transfer learning potential and hence given a higher score. On the other hand, a negative or smaller cosine similarity with randomly selected gradients is an indicator for interference with the previously learned knowledge.

5.2 Sample selection by learning a scoring network

5.2.1 Correcting for true TD-error

[26] describes a modification to PER where a simple linear model is learned to predict the current sum of all the temporal-difference errors when the transitions are re-evaluated on the current critic network. The features to the model are the stored sum and the sum of the time-stamps of transitions (training iteration at which the transition was collected). The feature selection appears to be an empirically verified fact even though it is not clear why the sum of time-stamps is a good predictor of the actual TD-error sum. The sampling from the buffer is still done according to the stored priorities however the following weight re-adjustment is done for each sample τ_i .

$$w_i = (P_{\text{new}}(\tau_i)/P_{\text{old}}(\tau_i))^\beta \quad (31)$$

where $P_{\text{new}}, P_{\text{old}(i)}$ are probabilities computed using the stored TD-error and stored sum and current TD-error and the predicted sum by the network. The primary reason for learning a simple network for sum prediction is the computation efficiency of not having to recompute the sum at each training iteration. The true-sum needed for training the sum-prediction network is done every K steps to reduce overhead. Moreover, not updating the prediction network regularly is motivated by the assumption that the networks change slowly thereby affecting the sum only gradually.

5.2.2 Training a sampling network based on proxy reward

[27] [28] trains a sampling network that outputs the probability of sampling a given transition. A proxy reward is used to define the optimisation objective for sampling policy. The exact training scheme presented in these papers doesn't appear to follow from rigorous grounds. However we use the same proxy reward to give the following procedure. Given a mini-batch of transitions \mathcal{B} and the scoring network giving priority scores for each transition we can define the probability for the mini-batch

$$P(\mathcal{B}|\theta) = \prod_i p(\tau_i; \theta) \quad (32)$$

Where $p(\tau_i; \theta)$ is the probability assigned to transition τ_i by the scoring network. We define as in [27] the *learning reward* associated with the given mini-batch \mathcal{B} , update of the networks as the difference in the total episodic reward induced by the policy before and after the update,

$$R(\mathcal{B}) = R_{RL}^+ - R_{RL}^- \quad (33)$$

Here R_{RL}^+, R_{RL}^- are total episodic reward on two trajectories generated by the post-update and pre-update policies resp. Optimization objective for the scoring network can now be defined as

$$\mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{B} \sim P(\mathcal{B}|\theta)} [R(\mathcal{B})] \quad (34)$$

Which gives,

$$\nabla_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{B} \sim P(\mathcal{B}|\theta)} [R(\mathcal{B})] = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{B} \sim P(\mathcal{B}|\theta)} \left[\sum_{\tau_i \in \mathcal{B}} \nabla_{\theta} \log p(\tau_i; \theta) \right] \quad (35)$$

5.3 Resampling and Re-weighting

5.3.1 Equivalent loss functions

When the mini-batch is sampled from the replay buffer with a set of probabilities assigned to each transition $\tau \rightarrow p(\tau)$, it is instructive to think of the replay buffer as describing a discrete random variable that takes values in the set of transitions stored in the buffer. Thus each training update corresponds to minimizing the following objective

$$\mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim p(\tau)} [L(\tau)] \quad (36)$$

where L is loss function used (ex, squared TD-error for the critic-network). Given another set of probabilities assigned to the transitions $\tau \rightarrow q(\tau)$, (A.1) gives,

$$\mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim p(\tau)} [L(\tau)] = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim q(\tau)} \left[\frac{p(\tau)}{q(\tau)} L(\tau) \right] \quad (37)$$

Given that the mini-batches of size M , $\mathcal{B}_p, \mathcal{B}_q$ are sampled according to the distributions p, q respectively, both $\frac{1}{M} \sum_{\tau \in \mathcal{B}_p} L(\tau)$, $\frac{1}{M} \sum_{\tau \in \mathcal{B}_q} \frac{p(\tau)}{q(\tau)} L(\tau)$ become unbiased estimators of (36) even though the variance of the second estimator will usually be higher. This provides a way to use a computationally cheaper sampling strategy (ex. uniform sampling) and still get an estimate of the gradient update (perhaps of higher variance) by using a redefined loss function \tilde{L} ,

$$\tilde{L}(\tau) = \frac{p(\tau)}{q(\tau)} L(\tau) \quad (38)$$

[29] provides an empirical study of using an equivalent loss functions for uniform sampling, $u(\tau)$ for weight-adjusted PER, $\mathcal{L}_{\text{W-PER}}$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{W-PER}}(\tau_i) = w(\tau_i) \frac{1}{p} (\delta(\tau_i))^p \quad (39)$$

where,

$$w(\tau) = \frac{\tilde{w}(\tau)}{\max\{\tilde{w}(\tau')\}} \quad \tilde{w}(\tau) = \left(\frac{1}{P(\tau)N} \right)^{\beta} \quad (40)$$

and

$$P(\tau) = \frac{|\delta(\tau)|^{\alpha} + \epsilon}{\sum_{\tau'} |\delta(\tau')|^{\alpha} + \epsilon} \quad (41)$$

is the sampling probability for PER. The equivalent loss-function for the uniform sampling is,

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{W-PER}}^{\text{equiv}} = \frac{\eta N}{p + \alpha - \alpha\beta} |\delta(\tau)|^{p+\alpha-\alpha\beta}, \quad \eta = \frac{\min |\delta(\tau)|^{\alpha\beta}}{\sum_{\tau'} |\delta(\tau')|^{\alpha}} \quad (42)$$

5.3.2 Resampling for off-policy distribution shift

[30] gives an alternate method for accounting for the distributional shift of the transitions when the collection policy μ and the training policy π are different. The distribution of the transition $\tau = (s, a, s', r)$ generated by policy μ is given by

$$\mu(s)\mu(a|s)p(s'|s, a)r(r|s, a, s') \quad (43)$$

where $\mu(s)$ is the stationary distribution of states induced by policy μ . Given that expectation of loss-functions of interest is with respect distribution induced by the current policy, $\mu(s)\pi(a|s)p(s'|s, a)r(r|s, a, s')$ we can find the importance sampling ratio ρ_i for τ_i to be,

$$\rho_i = \frac{\mu(s)\pi(a|s)p(s'|s, a)r(r|s, a, s')}{\mu(s)\mu(a|s)p(s'|s, a)r(r|s, a, s')} = \frac{\pi(a|s)}{\mu(a|s)} \quad (44)$$

[30] shows empirically that using a replay buffer one can achieve much lower variance estimate by sampling the replay buffer with probabilities,

$$p(\tau) = \frac{\rho_\tau}{\sum_{\tau \in \mathcal{B}} \rho_\tau} \quad (45)$$

Moreover they prove that the bias of the estimator using the above sampling is equal to the bias of the weighted importance sampling estimator (A.2), thus, scales as $\mathcal{O}(1/|\mathcal{B}|)$

5.4 Long term and short-term episodic memories

5.4.1 Replay generation using GAN

[31] propose a complex training scheme with dual RL agents for short-term (STM) and long-term (LTM) learning. The task of the STM agent is to use a small FIFO replay buffer for RL training (ex. actor-critic, DQN). The LTM RL agent uses supervised learning by minimizing the MSE between the Q-network and policy-networks of the STM agent evaluated on the experience collected in the STM replay buffer. Instead of using a large replay buffer to store past experiences, they use a GAN network that generates experiences reflecting past data which itself is trained with a mix of data generated from pre-update GAN and from STM buffer. We believe that this model is too complex as the three different parts STM, LTM and GAN must interplay and learn synchronously even though it uses an interesting idea of knowledge distillation.

5.4.2 Dual replay buffers

In [32] two replay buffers are used. A small buffer \mathcal{D}_g for collecting the most recent experience for *near on-policy* training and a large buffer, \mathcal{D}_e that retains experiences with reservoir sampling which is used for exploration. The idea espoused in this work is that as the policy begins to converge it will narrow its search to a smaller region of state space and this might cause catastrophic forgetting of past behaviours. To remedy this situation a larger ratio of samples are drawn from the exploration buffer to reduce interference. [32] proposes an adaptive exploration ratio τ ,

$$\tau = \frac{n_b}{N} \tau_{\max} \quad (46)$$

Here given a random batch of states of size N , n_b is the number of states on which both the policy and the target-policy agree (or close to within a predefined threshold, ϵ for continuous action spaces, $\|a - a'\| \leq \epsilon$). This adaptive rate is re-adjusted at a fixed interval of training steps or as recommended in the paper, every time the target network is updated.

A Appendix

A.1 Importance sampling

Importance sampling is way to find the averages/ expectation with respect to a probability distribution, $p(x)$, that is different from the available sampling distribution $q(x)$.

Theorem A.1. Given probability distribution described by pdf or probability mass functions $p(x), q(x)$,

$$\mathbb{E}_{x \sim p(x)} [f(x)] = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim q(x)} \left[\frac{p(x)}{q(x)} f(x) \right] \quad (47)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p(x)} [f(x)] &= \int p(x) f(x) dx \\ &= \int q(x) \frac{p(x)}{q(x)} f(x) dx \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{x \sim q(x)} \left[\frac{p(x)}{q(x)} f(x) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

□

A.2 Weighted importance sampling

Weighted importance sampling is a variant of the above, that yields a *biased* but *consistent* estimator of the expectation that usually has much lower variance compared to the IS estimator.

Theorem A.2. The WIS estimator for a sample of size N from $q(x)$ is given by

$$\text{est-WIS} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N w(x_i) f(x_i) \quad (49)$$

where the weights $w(x_i)$ are the normalised importance sampling weights,

$$w(x_i) = \frac{\tilde{w}(x_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^N \tilde{w}(x_j)} \quad \tilde{w}(x_i) = \frac{p(x_i)}{q(x_i)} \quad (50)$$

Moreover this is a consistent estimator,

$$\text{est-WIS} \rightarrow \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p(x)} [f(x)] \quad (51)$$

and

$$\text{Bias}(\text{est-WIS}) = \mathcal{O}(1/N) \quad (52)$$

A.3 Effective policy from replay buffer

Using the transitions sampled from replay buffer to train an RL agent has important implications as it alters the training distribution of data. Here we give a formal proof for the effective distribution of the

Theorem A.3. Let $\mu(a|s; \theta_t)$ be the policy (distribution) after t training iterations. Suppose for simplicity (can be generalised easily) 1 transition is collected before each training update. Moreover the training is done by using a FIFO replay buffer of size N and the mini-batch of transitions are sampled uniformly from the buffer. Then the effective-policy distribution the agent is being trained on at training iteration t is $\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \mu(a|s; \theta_{t-i})$

Proof. Let $L(\tau)$ be the loss function for RL (actor or critic) evaluated on a transition τ . We first observe that using a uniformly sampled mini-batch of transitions \mathcal{B} , we have the following loss for the training update,

$$\frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \sum_{\tau \in \mathcal{B}} L(\tau) \quad (53)$$

Replay buffer with uniform sampling with replacement at training iteration t is a uniform discrete random variable taking values in the transitions that are stored there, denoted \mathcal{D} . Hence by central limit theorem we see that (53) is an estimator for the following expectation,

$$\mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \mathcal{D}} [L(\tau)] = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\tau \in \mathcal{D}} L(\tau) \quad (54)$$

Now consider a transition generated at training iteration k ,

$$\tau := (s_i, a_i, s_{i+1}) \sim \mu(s_i) \mu(a_i | s_i; \theta_k) p(s_{i+1} | s_i, a_i) =: p_k(\tau) \quad (55)$$

From this we see that $L(\tau)$ is a single sample estimator of the following expectation,

$$\mathbb{E}_{\tau' \sim p_k} [L(\tau')] \quad (56)$$

Substituting we see that (54) is an estimator for,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\tau \in \mathcal{D}} \mathbb{E}_{\tau' \sim p_k} [L(\tau')] &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k \in [t-N+1, \dots, t]} \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim p_k} [L(\tau)] \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k \in [t-N+1, \dots, t]} \int p(\tau) L(\tau) d\tau \\ &= \int \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k \in [t-N+1, \dots, t]} p(\tau) L(\tau) d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

Thus we see (53) can be interpreted as an estimator for the expectation of $L(\tau)$ under the distribution $\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k \in [t-N+1, \dots, t]} p(\tau)$, which in turn implies that this is induced by the *effective policy distribution* $\mu_{eff}(a|s) := \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k \in [t-N+1, \dots, t]} \mu(a|s; \theta_k)$ \square

It is instructive to note that the pointwise change in this effective distribution after 1 training iteration is given by,

$$\frac{(\mu(a|s; \theta_{t+1}) - \mu(a|s; \theta_{t-N+1}))}{N} \quad (58)$$

We see that the change is suppressed by the factor $1/N$, hence the larger the size of the replay buffer the smaller the change and more *stationary* the effective distribution.

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